

Breaking Ground and Shaping the Future: P2Green's Milestones and Visionary Initiatives Propel Sustainable Nutrient Management

March 2024

Impactful Actions Across Pilot Regions

In the **Swedish pilot region**, we dedicated resources developing a urine-diverting insert tailored for blue chemical toilets, building on lessons learned from a previous prototype. The initiation of a larger-scale urine collection and drying operation on the mainland of Sweden marked a crucial step in our commitment to sustainable practices. Standardizing drying levels for automated processes, optimizing chemical addition for urine stabilization, and successfully upscaling the urine pelletizing process to a larger scale were key achievements, reinforcing our dedication to efficient and environmentally conscious resource management.

In the **German pilot region**, key accomplishments include the procurement of composting containers, with both the sanitization and composting containers successfully delivered. Goldeimer, our valued partner, effectively implemented feces collection and treatment containers. The notable achievement of obtaining approval for field trials, scheduled to commence in March 2024, underscores our commitment to advancing innovative solutions. Additionally, we initiated the building permission process, setting the stage for further development and implementation.

In the **Spanish pilot region**, the Water Reclamation Plant, equipped with tertiary treatment, is now operational, comprising three phases: disc filtration, ozone disinfection, and NaClO dosage. With a treatment capacity of 10 m³/day, the reclaimed water demonstrates high biofertilizer value with NPK content. In the field test and crops domain, 60 avocado (Hass) and 60 mango (Osteen) trees were planted across an 850 m² surface area. The team designed a comparative analysis involving three fertigation treatments (T1, T2 & T3) using both conventional and reclaimed water. The Smart Irrigation Tool showcased accomplishments like the installation of lysimeters, tensiometers, and electronic sensors, enabling data collection on soil parameters. The irrigation system is now poised for a transition from manual to fully automatic operation, reflecting advancements in technology. An extensive analysis and monitoring campaign for water, crops, and soil calibration of sensors further underscores our commitment to innovation and sustainable practices in water resource utilization.

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Events, Meetings and Workshops

On June 9, 2023, P2GreenN took the stage at **Green Week**, offering insights into its innovative approach towards sustainable nutrient management. The presentation emphasized the pivotal role of skills and upskilling for regional actors and local authorities in implementing effective nutrient recovery systems. The pilot regions showcased their goals and achievements, underlining the project's commitment to addressing environmental challenges and fostering a circular economy in agriculture.

P2GreenN made an appearance at the 87th **Thessaloniki International Fair (TIF)** through our consortium partner, the Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH). Taking place from September 9 to 17, TIF served as a platform for showcasing advancements in technology, environment, energy, education, and start-ups. CERTH's participation highlighted P2GreenN's commitment to presenting innovative solutions within Greece's socio-economic landscape, contributing to the fair's diverse range of impactful initiatives.

Our consortium partners from CERTH represented P2GreenN at the **Biorural Annual Meeting** in Rome on October 9-10 and actively engaged by presenting key facets of our project. The event provided an excellent opportunity to showcase the P2GreenN initiative, sharing insights and updates with experts in bio-rural development.

P2GreenN's 2nd **Transnational Meeting** in Málaga was a resounding success! Between October 16th and 19th, the Consortium convened to discuss sustainability, share knowledge, and engage in impactful discussions. The meeting featured comprehensive reviews of project milestones and achievements, fostering collaboration and innovation. Partners explored the Spanish pilot site at TROPS, participated in knowledge-sharing workshops, and benefited from a cross-fertilization workshop with key stakeholders. Special thanks to partners for their invaluable contributions. The P2GreenN Consortium looks forward to future successes with unwavering commitment to sustainability and collaboration. Follow #P2GreenN for updates on this remarkable project's journey.

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The 1st **Cross-Fertilisation Workshop** held on October 19, during P2GreenN's 2nd Transnational Meeting in Málaga, Spain, was a resounding success. This event gathered experts, stakeholders, and pioneers in sustainable agriculture, fertilizer management, and wastewater utilization for knowledge exchange. Featuring distinguished speakers, including representatives from the European Commission and various pilot regions, the workshop aimed to foster collaboration, address challenges, and promote sustainable solutions. Attendees gained insights, addressed challenges, and explored opportunities for collaborative projects. The workshop also provided clarity on EU regulations and inspired initiatives for sustainable practices in agriculture. This event marked a critical step toward environmentally friendly nutrient management in agriculture, setting the stage for innovative solutions and positive change.

Future Plans

P2GreenN will participate in the **Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival** on March 11, 2024. This international conference, aligned with the European Commission's initiative, focuses on engaging youth in transformative changes. The event offers a platform to discuss the pivotal role of projects like P2GreenN in advancing the bioeconomy. With an agenda encompassing an in-depth project overview, partner interviews, presentations by young entrepreneurs, and a roundtable discussion, the conference aims to foster dialogue, raise awareness, and shape the future of EU Bioeconomy policies.

P2GreenN will actively participate in the **ESPP Workshop on Nutrient Recycling** on March 13-14, 2024. The event centers on policy tools supporting market pull for recycled nutrients, intending to foster the development of feasible and consensus-driven regulatory proposals for submission to the EC. This event plays a crucial role in shaping future nutrient reuse and recycling policies aligned with the EU Green Deal and Circular Economy Action Plan.

‘What is special about this project is that we are **changing the system’**
- **Anita Beblek**, Managing Director of the Project Coordinator

